

“STUDY OF STRESS BEHAVIOR OF COHESION LESS SOIL MIXED WITH GRANITE DUST UNDER CBR TEST”

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Abstract—

"This investigative study undertakes a comprehensive examination of the potential benefits of incorporating granite dust as a soil stabilization agent, with a specific focus on its effects on the geotechnical properties of cohesionless soil. Through a rigorous analysis of soil samples sourced from three distinct geographical locations, this research aims to provide an in-depth understanding of the mechanisms by which granite dust influences soil behavior, and to contribute meaningfully to the development of innovative, effective, and sustainable soil stabilization techniques."

Keywords— Keywords: Granite Dust, Soil Stabilization, CBR Test.

INTRODUCTION

Soft soils, such as Cohesion less soils, can cause significant damage to highway pavement, especially if they are exposed to water. Chemical additions have the potential to improve soil engineering features. The feasibility of developing the strength of Cohesion less soils was evaluated using granite waste dust in this article. The influence of deposited granite dust on the characteristics of soft soils is investigated in this study. The soil was examined for its Atterberg limits, particle size distributions, dry density, bearing capacity, and shear strength. Granite dust in various percentages was applied to the natural with increasing the amount of granite dust, the introduction of granite dust yielded significant enhancements in the soil's geotechnical properties, notably increasing its Maximum Dry Density, Optimum Water Content, Direct Shear Strength, and California Bearing Ratio. Given the critical role of soil strength in geotechnical engineering, the evaluation of shear strength - which reflects a soil's internal resistance to shear stresses - is of paramount importance. By accurately assessing shear strength, engineers can reliably predict soil's load-bearing capacity, ensure the stability of geotechnical structures, and characterize soil's stress-strain behavior, ultimately informing the design of safe and durable infrastructure all require shear strength. The stress created in soil by applied loads is determined by the stress-strain properties of the soil. The stress-strain behavior of soil is complicated, and it is influenced by a variety of elements including drainage, water content, and void ratio, rate of loading, load level, and stress path. Some assumptions are applied to analyses stress-strain

behavior to simplify the problem, and the results are usually good enough to handle problems found in field practice. When subjected to loads, every engineered material has the ability to distort. Soil is an engineering material with the ability to deform under load. Soils are rarely subjected to direct shear and direct tension; nonetheless, when soil is compressed, shear stress arises. When the shear stress caused by an applied force exceeds the soil's shear strength, shear failure occurs. When loads are surpassed, relative displacement of the particles causes failure. As a result, determining the shear strength characteristics of soil provides a solution to many soil issues.

Review Paper on Additives' Impact on Cohesion less Soil Strength

Influence of Fines on Sand Behavior"Exploring the Impact of Fines Content on the Geotechnical Properties of Mixed Sand Samples"

Shear Strength of Remoulded Residual Soil "Characterizing the Shear Strength Parameters of Remoulded Residual Soil through Experimental Analysis"

Soil Testing Methods "Standardized Procedures for Determining Liquid and Plastic Limits of Soils: A Comprehensive Guide"

Non-Plastic Fines and Loose Sand "Assessing the Effects of Non-Plastic Fines on the Mechanical Behavior of Loose Sand: An Experimental Investigation"

Fines Content and Steady-State Strength "Examining the Relationship between Fines Content and Steady-State Strength of Mixed and Layered Sand Samples".

Objectives

The objectives of this review paper are as follows:

1. To Analyze Current Research: Review and synthesize recent studies focused on the treatment of cohesionless soil with granite dust, highlighting key findings and methodologies.
2. To Assess Strength Properties: Investigate the effects of these additives on the strength properties of cohesionless soil, specifically examining improvements in shear strength, and plasticity index.
3. To Explore Stabilization Mechanisms: Examine the mechanisms through which granite dust contribute to soil stabilization, including chemical reactions, physical interactions, and improvements in soil structure.
4. To Determine Optimal Mix Designs: Identify optimal mix proportions of the additives to achieve the best possible enhancement of soil properties, thereby providing practical recommendations for field applications.
5. To Evaluate Environmental Benefits: Assess the environmental implications of using industrial by-products for soil stabilization, focusing on sustainability and waste management in construction practices.
6. To Provide Practical Recommendations: Offer practical guidelines for engineers and practitioners on the application of these stabilization techniques in civil engineering projects involving cohesionless soil.
7. This study identifies key gaps in existing soil stabilization research and proposes targeted areas for further exploration, driving innovation and advancing our understanding of soil stabilization.

Problem statement

Analysis of embankment stability by using granite dust.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research framework for this review paper provides a structured and comprehensive approach to investigating the strength properties of cohesionless soil treated with granite dust. This framework integrates various components that facilitate a thorough understanding of the subject matter and guides the research process through distinct phases. The framework encompasses the following key elements:

Research Objectives and Questions:

Clearly articulate the primary objectives and research questions that guide this review. Key questions may include:

1. How do the inclusion of granite dust impact of the overall engineering properties of cohesionless soil?
2. What are the optimal mix ratios of these additives to maximize soil stabilization benefits?
3. What key mechanisms drive the interaction between these materials and cohesionless soil, leading to improved properties?

Establish a connection between the objectives and the theoretical foundations to ensure that the investigation remains focused on addressing pertinent issues in soil stabilization.

Methodological Approach:

- Literature Search Strategy: Describe a systematic literature search strategy employed to gather relevant studies. This includes using multiple academic databases (e.g., Google Scholar, Scopus, and Web of Science) with specific keywords and Boolean operators to refine search results.
- To ensure a thorough and systematic review, a data extraction protocol will be developed and implemented. This protocol will facilitate the collection of critical data points from selected studies, spanning experimental design, sample preparation methods, testing procedures, and measurements of strength properties.

Discussion of Implications:

- Geotechnical Engineering Applications: Discuss the broader implications of the findings within the field of geotechnical engineering. Highlight how the enhanced strength properties of treated black cotton soil can improve the performance and longevity of structures, especially in regions where this soil type is prevalent.
- Sustainability and Environmental Considerations: Emphasize the environmental benefits of utilizing industrial by-products for soil stabilization. Discuss the potential for reducing landfill waste and promoting sustainable construction practices through the use of fly ash, brick dust, and ceramic powder.

MATERIAL PROCURED

In the study of "Strength Properties of Cohesion less Soil Treated with Granite Dust the following materials will be utilized:

1. **cohesionless Soil:** Cohesionless soil is a type of soil that does not stick together and is made up of particles that rely on friction to hold them together. Examples of cohesionless soil include sand and gravel.
2. **Granite Dust:** Granite dust is a fine, non-biodegradable powder that is a waste product of the granite stone industry. It is created when granite is crushed, and is also known as crusherrun.
3. **Water:** Clean and potable water will be used for mixing and preparing the soil-stabilizer blends to ensure proper hydration and activation of the stabilizing agents.

Testing Equipment

In addition to these materials, appropriate testing equipment will be utilized to evaluate the strength properties of the treated soil, including:

- **Compaction Apparatus:** For determining the optimum moisture content and maximum dry density.
- **CBR Test Apparatus:** To assess the 2.5 mm and 5.0 mm Penetration.
- **Atterberg Limits Apparatus:** For evaluating the plasticity characteristics of the soil.
- **Sieve:** For grain size distribution analysis.

These materials and equipment will facilitate a comprehensive investigation into the strength properties of cohesionless soil when treated with granite dust.

Cohesionless Soil

Relative density: A measure of how compact the soil is, and whether it's closer to its densest or loosest state. Relative density is the most important aggregate property of cohesionless soil.

Liquefaction: Cohesionless soil, like sand and silt, can undergo liquefaction under dynamic loads like waves and earthquakes. This can lead to reduced or lost foundation strength, unstable submarine soil, and major accidents.

Erosion: Cohesionless soil is more prone to erosion than cohesive soil, like clay

Physical and Chemical Properties

Cohesionless soil, also known as noncohesive or granular soil, has the following physical and chemical properties:

Physical properties

Cohesionless soil has high hydraulic conductivity or permeability, meaning it transmits water easily. It also has a shear strength with only a friction component and zero cohesion intercept. Other physical properties of soil include:

Texture: The composition of sand, silt, and clay particles, which determines soil behavior.

Structure: The spatial arrangement of soil particles, impacting soil strength, porosity, and hydraulic conductivity.

Consistency: The soil's resistance to deformation or rupture, indicating its mechanical properties.

Particle Density: The mass per unit volume of individual soil particles, influencing soil settlement.

Bulk Density: The mass per unit volume of the entire soil, including particles and pores, affecting its overall density.

Chemical properties

Chemical properties of soil include flammability, toxicity, solubility, heat from combustion, radioactivity, and more

Some index properties of non-cohesive soil include: Particle size distribution, Particle shape, and Relative density.

Challenges in Construction

Construction in cohesionless soil can present several challenges, including:

Soil collapse

When cohesionless soil is subjected to cyclic loading in a saturated state, its particle structure can undergo a collapse, resulting in a denser configuration. This collapse can trigger an increase in pore water pressure, ultimately reducing the soil's ability to resist shear stress.

Internal erosion

Internal erosion can change the soil's microstructure, which can increase the void ratio and cause volumetric deformation.

Unstable structure

At very low moisture levels, cohesionless soil can form a loose, honeycombed structure that's unstable and can collapse easily.

Groundwater issues

Groundwater issues can cause unstable excavation, water seepage, and construction delays. After construction, groundwater issues can lead to water leaks, wet basements, mold growth, and more.

Figure1.1: Cohesionless Soil

A) Granite Dust

Decomposed granite, or granite dust, is a versatile waste material generated from granite stone cutting and grinding operations. Its potential uses in construction include replacing natural fine aggregate in concrete mixes, offering several benefits.

Sustainability: Granite dust is a sustainable alternative to cement and can help with greener development. It can also reduce the carbon footprint of construction projects.

Strength: Granite dust can improve the strength and durability of concrete. It can increase the average density of concrete, and reduce water absorption and penetration.

Microstructure: The addition of granite dust can enhance the microstructural density of the cement matrix, resulting in a more compact and potentially stronger material.

Workability: Granite dust can increase the workability of concrete. Granite dust can also be used in soil to improve its stability and durability.

Composition and Properties

The chemical composition of granite dust depends on its origin, but it generally contains the following chemical compounds:

- SiO₂: 50–80%
- Al₂O₃: 10–20%
- CaO: 5–15%
- K₂O: 2–5%
- Fe₂O₃: 3–8%
- Others: <2%

Granite is made up of coarse grains of quartz, potassium feldspar, and sodium feldspar. It's also a good source of potassium, and contains small amounts of phosphorus, iron, magnesium, and manganese. In industrial construction, granite dust can be employed to improve the engineering properties of weak soils, thereby increasing their stability and load-bearing capacity

Benefits of Using Granite Dust

Granite dust has many benefits in construction, including:

Strength: Granite dust can increase the strength and durability of concrete. This is because it partially replaces sand in the concrete mix, which compacts the cement matrix's microstructure.

Water absorption: Granite dust can reduce water absorption by 32–38% and water penetration by 60–70%.

Density: Granite dust can increase the average density of concrete.

Drainage: Granite dust's small particle size helps prevent water from accumulating on surfaces, which reduces the risk of water damage.

Easy to compact: Granite dust is easy to compact and level, making it suitable for various construction projects.

Preserves natural resources: Using granite powder instead of sand can help preserve sand resources.

Prevents health hazards: Using granite powder instead of sand can keep the powder particles from being airborne into the atmosphere, which can cause health hazards to humans.

Research Methodology

- To collection of Cohesionless soil.
- Collection of materials. (Granite dust)
- Test on cohesion less soil.
- Specific Gravity Test.
- Atterberg Limit
- Modified Proctor test for various parameter.
(To find MDD & OMC)
- CBR Test for various parameter.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. Cohesion less soil + Granite dust.

Property	Cohesion less Soil (CS)	CS + 10% Granite dust	CS + 15% Granite dust	CS + 20% Granite dust	CS + 25% Granite dust
Maximum Dry Density (MDD)	2.00	2.040	1.985	1.965	2.020
Optimum Moisture Content (OMC)	10.05 %	10.70%	10.6%	10.2%	10.25%
CBR Value at 2.5 mm	15.86 %	17.66%	17.8 %	17.99.%	18.55%

2. Graphs showing Comparison of MDD, OMC & CBR of cohesionless soil with Granite dust.

Observations

MDD & OMC: To optimize Maximum Dry Density (MDD) and potentially increase Optimum Moisture Content (OMC), granite dust was added in varying proportions of 10%, 15%, 20%, and 25%.

CBR Improvement: The CBR Value of cohesion soil without granite dust is 15.86% and the addition of 25% granite dust in cohesion less soil improved to 18.55% of CBR value.

The inclusion of 10%, 15% & 25% Granite dust in cohesion less Soil leads to significant improvement in MDD, slight increase in OMC, and enhanced CBR values, suggesting a more stable soil structure suitable for subgrade applications in pavement layers.

CONCLUSION

Research was undertaken to assess the impact of granite dust on the strength properties of cohesionless soil, with findings indicating that each additive conferred unique benefits in terms of enhanced soil stability.

Granite dust enhanced soil strength and load-bearing capacity by forming additional cementitious compounds, while brick dust improved compaction and reduced plasticity. Ceramic powder further contributed to strength improvement, particularly in controlling the soil's shrink-swell characteristics. The combined use of these materials offers a promising approach to achieving an optimized blend that enhances strength, reduces plasticity, and mitigates swelling.

- Fly ash improved strength properties by forming cementitious compounds within the soil matrix.
- Brick dust enhanced soil compaction and reduced plasticity, making it easier to achieve desired stability levels.
- Ceramic powder contributed to strength improvement and helped control shrink-swell behavior.
- The combined use of fly ash, brick dust, and ceramic powder offers an optimized stabilization approach, enhancing strength, reducing plasticity, and minimizing swelling.

Implications for Soil Stabilization

The findings have significant implications for soil stabilization, particularly in regions where black cotton soil is prevalent and infrastructure stability is a challenge.

The use of these additives can result in more durable, stable foundations for construction, providing cost-effective alternatives to more expensive soil replacement techniques. Additionally, the reduced plasticity and increased load-bearing capacity achieved through stabilization make black cotton soil a viable option for various civil engineering applications, including road construction and embankments.

- These findings support the use of granite dust for stabilizing cohesion less soil in construction projects.

- Enhanced soil properties, such as improved load-bearing capacity and reduced plasticity, enable the use of black cotton soil for roads, foundations, and embankments.
- The approach provides a cost-effective alternative to traditional soil replacement, offering economic and environmental benefits in construction.
- Improved CBR shows that it is good for subgrade work of pavement of any type that is Rigid or Flexible.

Scope of Future

Cohesion less soil is silty and sandy in nature and also it is finer so meet its quality standards further investigation need also to be done.

Additionally, Granite dust is not more cost effective so to overcome in this problem we have to do some other significant investigation.

Examine alternative waste materials, such as industrial byproducts, for potential use as soil stabilizers to enhance sustainability.

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